

Mortality rate from explorative thoracotomies for chest trauma according to brazilian hospital records

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Abstract

Introduction: Exploratory thoracotomy is mainly performed in emergencies, with high morbidity and mortality rates. The procedure has a significant economic and psychosocial impact. Despite technical advances and the consolidation of minimally invasive procedures, thoracotomy remains an essential approach in several clinical situations, both elective and emergency. The Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS), which serves the vast majority of the country's population, faces challenges related to the availability of resources, regional inequality in access to specialized services, and the overload of urgent and emergency services. In this sense, this study aims to analyze the hospital mortality rate related to traumatic thoracotomies performed in the SUS based on hospital records, seeking to understand the factors involved in negative outcomes and contribute to the strengthening of thoracic surgical care in Brazil.

Materials and Methods: This is an observational, retrospective, and descriptive study based on secondary data extracted from the SUS Hospital Information System (SIH/SUS), available in the DataSUS database, referring to hospital procedures in Brazil between 2008 and 2024, by place of admission, related to exploratory thoracotomy in trauma. **Results:** The findings of this study demonstrate a significant hospital mortality rate associated with thoracotomy in the SUS context, especially in emergency cases. The difference found between the outcomes of elective and emergency procedures highlights the importance of preoperative preparation. The variation in mortality rates between different regions of Brazil, with higher rates in the South and Southeast, may reflect the higher volume of procedures performed in these locations, including receiving more complex cases from other regions. **Conclusion:** Mortality remains high, especially in emergencies, indicating a need for improvements in trauma care and health policies. Despite the limitations of the study, it is necessary to improve the quality of records to combat underreporting.

Keywords: trauma, thorax, thoracotomy.

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Introduction

Thoracotomy is a surgical technique that involves opening the chest cavity through an incision in the anterolateral wall of the chest and is used to access intrathoracic structures such as the lungs, heart, large vessels, and mediastinum [1].

Despite technical advances and the consolidation of minimally invasive procedures, thoracotomy remains an essential approach in various clinical situations, both elective and emergency [2]. It is often indicated in cases of lung neoplasms, lung metastases [3], complex cardiovascular diseases [4] and severe chest trauma [5], and is considered a major procedure with potential life-threatening risks [6].

In recent decades, video-assisted thoracic surgery (VATS) has emerged as a less invasive alternative to traditional thoracotomy³. Several studies indicate that VATS is associated with lower rates of perioperative complications, shorter hospital stays, and reduced mortality [3,7,8]. However, in specific situations, such as in cases of extensive lung tumors, the presence of adhesions, complex anatomy, or the need for intraoperative conversion, thoracotomy remains the safest and most effective method [3,9]. Furthermore, in emergency contexts, such as penetrating chest trauma, cardiopulmonary arrest with cardiac tamponade, or massive hemothorax, thoracotomy is often the only alternative with the potential to save lives [5,6,10].

The literature also highlights that thoracotomy outcomes vary significantly depending on patient profiles and the conditions under which the surgery is performed¹¹. In patients undergoing emergency thoracotomy, hospital mortality can exceed 50% [6,10], especially among those with severe trauma or hemodynamic deterioration at the time of care [5]. In elective procedures, although mortality rates are lower, they can still be significant, particularly in the elderly, patients with multiple comorbidities, or when performed in institutions with lower surgical volume or by less specialized teams.

The type of surgical approach also directly influences the results. Studies comparing open thoracotomy and video-assisted surgery in different contexts — such as pulmonary lobectomy³, metastasis resection [3], valve surgery [4], and diaphragmatic hernia repair [14] — demonstrate consistent advantages of the minimally invasive technique in terms of hospital stay, pain, bleeding, and pulmonary and cardiac complications [7]. However, conversion from VATS to thoracotomy, when necessary, is not necessarily associated with worse outcomes.

In specific populations, such as children and the elderly, results also vary. In children, studies show that thoracotomy can be safe when properly indicated, without a significant increase in morbidity compared to VATS [15]. In elderly patients, especially those over 80 years of age, the risk of complications increases, making detailed preoperative planning, risk stratification, and careful choice of surgical approach essential.

The Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS), which serves the vast majority of the country's population, faces challenges related to the availability of resources, regional inequality in access to specialized services, and the overload of urgent and emergency services. The lack of comprehensive studies on hospital mortality rates associated with trauma thoracotomy in the Brazilian context makes it difficult to identify patterns, bottlenecks, and opportunities for improvement in thoracic surgical care.

Given this, it is essential to investigate and understand the results of these surgeries in Brazil, based on real data from clinical and hospital practice. Such an analysis can support strategies for improving the quality of care, optimizing resources, professional training, and reducing mortality, especially in highly complex and urgent contexts. In this sense, this study aims to analyze the hospital mortality rate related to traumatic thoracotomies performed in the SUS based on hospital records, seeking to understand the factors involved in negative outcomes and contribute to the strengthening of thoracic surgical care in Brazil.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is an observational, retrospective, and descriptive study based on secondary data extracted from the SUS Hospital Information

Figure 2: Mortality rate (%) from exploratory thoracotomy by region (2008–2024)

System (SIH/SUS), available in the DataSUS database, referring to hospital procedures in Brazil between 2008 and 2024, by place of hospitalization, related to exploratory thoracotomy in trauma.

The data obtained were processed using Microsoft Excel software, where tables and graphs related to the collected data were created, which can be verified through the TabNet portal, at the following access link: <https://datasus.saude.gov.br/>

To obtain data on the procedure, the term “exploratory thoracotomy” was searched in DataSUS. We describe the mortality rate in general terms in Brazil, the mortality rate by demographic regions (North, Northeast, Midwest, Southeast, South), the mortality rate related to the nature of care (elective or emergency), and length of hospitalization.

Regarding ethical considerations, this study was exempted from submission to a Research Ethics Committee, as it exclusively used publicly accessible data, in accordance with current legislation. Nevertheless, the researchers followed the ethical principles established by Resolution No. 466/2012 of the Brazilian National Health Council, ensuring confidentiality and responsible use of the analyzed information.

RESULTS

The mortality rate from exploration thoracotomies, according to Figure 1, showed a slight reduction from 2008 (17.4) to 2024 (16.2), although with oscillations during the intermediate period. Compared to the previous year, in 2009 (16.7) there was a decrease of 0.8, in 2010 (17.2). No período da pandemia, a variação não foi estatisticamente significativa. In this regard, it is noteworthy that in 2014 and 2020 this rate reached its peak (20.4), whereas 2024 recorded the lowest value (16.2).

Figure 1: Mortality rate (%) from exploratory thoracotomy (2008–2024)

In addition, according to Figure 2, there are marked variations among the regions regarding the mortality rate from exploratory thoracotomy. The North region maintained the lowest rates throughout the period, with a notable decline from 16.7% in 2020 to 9.8% in 2024. The Northeast showed relative stability, starting at 17.3% in 2008 and ending at 15.9% in 2024. The Southeast and South concentrated the highest rates, with peaks of 24.7% in 2014 and 25.5% in 2021, respectively. Although the Southeast showed a decline in recent years, reaching 15.8% in 2024, the South continued to rise, reaching 23.9% in the same period. The Center-West, after a reduction from

2008 (16.9%) to 2019 (13.8%), recorded an increase in 2020, peaking at 24.2%, and later decreased again, reaching 14.4% in 2024. According to Figure 3, procedures performed as emergencies show significantly higher mortality rates compared to elective procedures throughout the entire study period. Elective mortality rates remained consistently lower over the years, ranging from 15.84% (2014) to 7.98% (2022), with a general downward trend until 2022, although oscillations were observed in the following two years (13.47% in 2023 and 10.46% in 2024). Emergency cases, on the other hand, maintained high and relatively stable rates, always above 18%, with a peak in 2020 (21.82%).

Figure 3: Mortality rate (%) by type of care (elective vs. emergency)

As shown in Figure 4, most hospitalizations and deaths occurred when the procedure was performed as an emergency rather than electively. Nevertheless, regardless of the type of care, there was an overall reduction in both hospitalizations and deaths from 2008 to 2024, despite oscillations during the intermediate years. The peak of elective hospitalizations was in 2008 (751), while emergency hospitalizations peaked in 2009 (2,424). The highest number of elective deaths

occurred in 2014 (89), whereas emergency deaths peaked in 2008 (461). Based on these data, the average relative risk (RR) of death from emergency exploratory thoracotomy calculated for the study period was 1.59, indicating that patients undergoing the procedure as an emergency had, on average, a 1.59 times greater likelihood of death compared to when it was performed electively.

Figure 4: Hospitalizations and deaths related to exploratory thoracotomy

DISCUSSION

Thoracotomy is a highly complex surgical procedure, often reserved for critical situations such as chest trauma, severe pulmonary

complications, and vascular injuries, where urgent interventions are necessary to preserve the patient's life.

The findings of this study demonstrate a significant hospital mortality rate associated with thoracotomy in the context of the SUS, especially

in emergency cases. This finding is consistent with that observed in studies such as Emergency Resuscitative Thoracotomy: A Nationwide Analysis of Outcomes and Predictors of Futility [5] and Abbreviated Thoracotomy and Temporary Chest Closure: An Application of Damage Control After Thoracic Trauma [6], which report high mortality rates in emergency thoracotomies, given the severe clinical conditions that motivate the intervention.

The average relative risk of death from emergency exploratory thoracotomy is 1.59, consistent with previous studies indicating significantly higher mortality in non-elective approaches. The difference found between the outcomes of elective and emergency procedures highlights the importance of preoperative preparation. In elective interventions, adequate time for patient assessment and stabilization favors better postoperative outcomes, while in emergencies, the often-unstable clinical condition and the need for immediate response increase the risk of mortality [2,5].

The variation in mortality rates between different regions of Brazil, with the highest rates in the South and Southeast, may reflect the greater volume of procedures performed in these locations, including receiving more complex cases from other regions. Although these centers have greater infrastructure and specialists, the profile of patients and the severity of cases may justify the observed lethality. The North region, in turn, had the lowest mortality rates, which should be interpreted with caution, as the lower availability of specialized services may influence both the number and nature of procedures performed.

The sharp increase in mortality related to this procedure in 2020 coincides with the most critical period of the COVID-19 pandemic, which severely impacted the functioning of the healthcare system, leading to the postponement of elective procedures and the overloading of emergency services. This condition may have worsened the profile of patients operated on during that period, contributing to an increase in hospital mortality, as also observed in the studies Decreased In-hospital Mortality after Lobectomy Using Video-Assisted Thoracoscopic Surgery Compared to Open Thoracotomy [7] and Intensive care unit (ICU) readmission after major lung resection: Prevalence, patterns, and mortality [10].

Although there is a downward trend in mortality in the final years of the historical series, rates remain high. It is important to consider that Brazil has many cities with high rates of urban violence, a shortage of labor in the public health system, strong socioeconomic inequality, and high disparity in the distribution of specialist surgeons and public service infrastructure. This situation may justify the high rates observed, even though advances in the regionalization of health care have been recognized. Brazil's vast territorial extension with its multiple contrasts implies a worsening of mortality rates.

Among the limitations of this study, we highlight the use of secondary data from the SIH/SUS, subject to underreporting and inconsistencies in registration, in addition to the absence of detailed clinical information, such as comorbidity profiles, case severity, and the experience of surgical teams. These restrictions limit the interpretation of the results and prevent the identification of direct causal relationships.

Despite these limitations, the findings reinforce the need for continued investment in professional training, hospital infrastructure, and the organization of care networks that ensure early and qualified access to treatment for thoracic conditions, notably traumatic ones. In addition, the incorporation of enhanced recovery strategies in the postoperative period has shown potential in reducing pulmonary and cardiac complications, contributing to better outcomes in patients undergoing thoracotomy [8].

CONCLUSION

There was a general trend toward reduced mortality, although with significant fluctuations over the years and significant regional disparities. The persistence of high mortality rates, especially in more developed regions and in emergency contexts, highlights the complexity of the procedure and the influence of systemic and structural factors on the outcome. The data obtained reinforce the need for public policies aimed at improving the quality of surgical care, reducing regional inequalities, and expanding access to adequate treatment. It is also necessary to improve the quality of information recorded in the SUS, definitively combating underreporting.

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